

Translanguaging in Practice: Exploring Translanguaging Pedagogical Approaches with English Language Learners

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Abstract: *Translanguaging is a pedagogical classroom approach that utilises learners' full range of linguistic resources in their learning. It not only brings learners' languages into the classroom but uses them in meaningful pedagogic ways. Despite the value of learners' languages being increasingly understood amongst teachers in schools and amongst pre-service teachers, the question of how to practically apply translanguaging pedagogy in classrooms remains unknown or a challenge for many teachers. This article uses reflective practice to illustrate how a collaborative partnership between in-service and pre-service teachers, and the researcher-lecturer, explores translanguaging within one school context. It outlines the challenges faced by teacher practitioners and the benefits of this approach for English language learners. The article also offers considerations for the approach in other contexts.*

Keywords: Translanguaging, ESL, EAL, EFL, English, second language learning

Introduction

Many English as an additional language (EAL) and English as a foreign language (EFL) programs focus solely on learners' English language skills and English is often the only language used in these programs. This practice ignores learners' home languages and does not make any connections between their first language (L1) and the second language (L2). This is a problem because learning builds on students' prior knowledge and experiences, and by ignoring the knowledge and experiences that are in L1, educators are not building from students' current knowledge. It also ignores the fact that knowledge and skills across languages are interconnected and should be used together as learning resources. Therefore, it is important for learners' home languages to have a place in their learning of EAL and EFL.

Teacher practitioners are increasingly understanding the importance of learners' languages to their learning, however, there is a limited understanding of ways to do this and there remains minimal practical uptake of methods to bring learners' languages into classroom practice. In particular,

teacher practitioners who are monolingual English speakers or do not share the additional languages of their students, are unsure how they could include languages other than English into their practice. So, in this article, translanguaging is explored as a practical approach to bring learners' home languages into the classroom and utilise them as learning resources. It not only invites all languages into classrooms and acknowledges learners' linguistic skills across languages, but also invites their experiences and cultural knowledge that is tied with the home language into the classroom and strives to utilise them in meaningful pedagogic ways. Importantly, there is not a requirement for teachers to know these languages to bring them into their classrooms.

To address the need for a practical uptake of translanguaging, a collaboration of teacher practitioners, including in-service teachers, university pre-service teachers and the lecturer-research-author, worked together to translate translanguaging theory to practice and trial translanguaging approaches with EAL students in one linguistically and culturally diverse primary school context in Melbourne, Australia. Reflective practice is used to share the challenges and concerns teacher-practitioners held and then discuss the benefits to English language learners when their home languages were used in their learning. This work aims to share practical approaches and implications of translanguaging so that other teacher-practitioners can more fully understand what translanguaging theory can look like in practice and consider how it may be used in their own teaching contexts.

Translanguaging: A Review of the Literature

Translanguaging is when bilingual or multilingual learners use their full range of languages in the classroom. Languages are not separated for different tasks, but rather, are mixed to be used as resources in various ways and for various purposes. This reflects an understanding that "... knowledge of their multiple languages is interconnected and integrated..." (Department of Education and Training Victoria, 2020, p.1). For bilingual and multilingual learners, languages are "... tools in their communicative toolkits, which they use flexibly according to need and circumstance" and restricting this use would be "...like telling a carpenter to build a house using only half of the tools in his or her toolbox" (Faulstich, 2015, p. 105). In this way, translanguaging focuses on the 'language user' (Baynham & Lee, 2019) and "...there are no clear-cut boundaries between the languages..." (García, 2009, p.115). This practice recognises the "interdependence of skills and knowledge across languages" (Creese & Blackledge, 2010).

New learning builds from learners' prior knowledge and experiences, and learners' languages are an integral aspect of that (Wilks-Smith, 2017). There is a need to understand and utilise the skills, knowledge and understandings that students have that is in their home languages so that students' prior knowledge that is encoded in their home languages can be used as resources to draw from. In this way, building on students' existing linguistic resources form springboards for their further classroom learning (Somerville, Sawyer & D'warte, 2016).

Translanguaging supports the understanding and learning of academic content (García & Kleyn, 2016) and activates and extends conceptual knowledge (Cummins & Persad, 2014). It helps EAL learners make links between their languages and experiences outside and within school (Conteh, 2018) and helps "... expand and re-situate the meanings they can already make, and the concepts they already have, to engage with the curriculum" (Feez & Harper, 2021, p.12). Using home languages with other home language speakers can help learners understand informational content,

share their language learning experiences and supports their engagement in their learning (Chau, 2007). Including home languages in learning also benefits learners' thinking because it can "... facilitate thought processes through the home language..." (French, 2016, p.309) and activates higher order thinking skills (García, 2009). It also helps learners process new and complex material (Swain and Lapkin, 2013).

The use of home languages also supports L2 English literacy acquisition at school (Liu, 2010). Home languages may be used to check comprehension, to clarify meaning, and to work out L2 meaning and decide on L2 words (Chau, 2007). Home languages may also support students to generate responses in L2 by using L1 with peers to negotiate meaning and form L2 utterances together. This shows how translanguaging can be used with EAL learners to "...support their understanding of content, develop their language performances, and buttress their socioemotional development" (García & Kleyn, 2016, p.14). Therefore, translanguaging provides a powerful tool "...to support language, literacy, conceptual learning, and access to information" (French, 2016, p.309). This demonstrates the multiple benefits of translanguaging to provide "...access to additional cognitive tools, further language learning ability, expanded spheres of communication, and affective development" (French, 2016, p.304). Translanguaging not only gives visibility to students' languages and places value on them (Pacheco & Miller, 2016) but also importantly, has benefits for students' learning of new academic content and their L2 English development. So, beyond allowing languages to be used in classrooms, the greatest benefit for EAL learners is realised when their multilingual resources are purposefully integrated into learning.

In practice however, languages are most commonly separated and L1 rarely has a role in L2 EAL or EFL learning. In EAL contexts, such as Australia, English is the language of school, and it is uncommon for learners' home languages to be used at all. In a Polish EFL context, an English-only method for EFL learning is most common and L1 Polish is avoided despite this being a shared language amongst teachers and learners (Sobkowiak, 2022). Similarly, in a South Korean EFL context, the most common practice is to separate languages and so L1 does not play a role in L2 English learning (Rabidge, 2020). The situation has been different however in Japanese EFL contexts, where L2 English education was traditionally taught through the medium of L1 Japanese until a policy change to English- EFL instruction (Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology (MEXT), 2011; MEXT 2014) which mandated that English classes be conducted only in English. This created a move from L1 Japanese-medium to L2 English-medium classes (Turnbull, 2018). These examples show that in each of these diverse EAL and EFL contexts, languages are separated and translanguaging is not used. Despite the increasing theoretical knowledge about translanguaging, there remains limited practical application in EAL and EFL classrooms. It is for this reason that this article shares practical examples of translanguaging in classrooms to meet that need.

Theoretical Framework

This article uses reflective practice as a theoretical framework to illustrate and discuss a collaboration of exploratory practice using translanguaging approaches with English language learners in one school context. Reflective practice is "... a cognitive, emotional process accompanied by a set of attitudes in which language teachers systematically collect data about their practice and, while engaging in dialogue with others, use the data to make informed decisions about their practice..."

(Farrell, 2022, p.47). Reflective practice involves informed and considered action in teaching and is a method for teachers to understand what they know and do in practice and learn through their teaching with the dual aims to improve their teaching and improve student learning. Farrell's framework of reflective practice for language teachers (Farrell, 2015; 2022) has been designed for the teaching of English to speakers of other languages (TESOL), including teaching English as a foreign language (EFL) and English as a second language (ESL) so it is particularly suited to these contexts and relevant for the current work. Farrell's framework supports language teachers to practically operationalise the concept of reflection, leading to change and professional growth and supporting teachers to make informed decisions about their teaching.

As an underlying philosophy, praxis aims to make research and theories applicable for teaching practice, and reflective practice does this by being practice focussed and involving theory-informed practice. In this article, praxis bridges translanguaging theories and research with practice to enable teacher practitioners to use translanguaging pedagogies in their own teaching context. It has a strong focus on practical pedagogical implications to drive improvements in teaching and learning. Reflective practice is used in this work to illustrate both a translanguaging pedagogical approach in context and demonstrate a model of collaboration between in-service and pre-service teachers and a lecturer-researcher to collaboratively explore this practice. Through this process, this article aims to contribute to teacher understandings about translanguaging and to share practical examples of translanguaging with English language learners that may stimulate ideas for teachers to use in their own contexts. What follows is an examination of translating translanguaging theory to practice in one English as an additional language learning context using reflective practice.

Translanguaging in One School Context

This section describes the collaborative approach to embedding translanguaging in one school context. An overview of the context and pedagogic rationale is provided, followed by a description of the classroom approach. A discussion based on the lecturer-researcher-author's personal reflections of the experience is shared leading to a discussion of considerations for other teachers in other contexts.

Background Context

In the linguistically and culturally diverse school context of Melbourne, Australia, all teachers, irrespective of year level or teaching discipline, are in fact teachers of English as an additional language because on average, thirty-three percent of students in their classes have English as a second or further language (Victorian State Government Department of Education and Training, 2020). Teachers of all curriculum areas need to use the English as an additional language (EAL) curriculum (VCAA, 2020) to support these students to develop English and address their learning needs. The EAL curriculum "... supports teachers to recognise students' existing languages and leverage them for learning English, new conceptual and cultural knowledge and skills" (Victorian State Government Department of Education and Training, 2021). This identifies the importance of learners' languages for their learning of English as an additional language, however, how to practically enact recognising and leveraging students' languages in classrooms remains a question for many teachers and is something rarely done in classroom practice. In an attempt to address

this, I (lecturer-researcher-author) explored the use of a translanguaging pedagogical approach to recognise and leverage students' languages in one primary school context in Melbourne Australia with in-service and pre-service teachers.

The pre-service teachers that were involved in the collaboration were enrolled in the teaching English to speakers of other languages (TESOL) elective course over one semester in the Bachelor of Education degree at a university in Melbourne, Australia. This is a unique course offering that includes on-campus university work with site-based in-school teaching and learning experiences. Through the TESOL course, students gain EAL-specific teaching methodology knowledge and teaching experience while directly being able to try out the new learnings from their course in action in a school. This model allows students to engage with course content while simultaneously translating their learnings into teaching practice.

The primary school that was the context for the exploration has a total of 324 students enrolled at the school and over half of these students are from language backgrounds other than English (LBOTE). Of these students, 85 students are within their first 5 years of English learning so receive support from an EAL program. These students are spread across the year levels from Prep (the first year of primary school) to Year 6. Part of the EAL support in the school includes the university-run EAL program that I coordinate with my pre-service teachers. Each pre-service teacher is paired with an EAL buddy to work one-on-one with one afternoon a week throughout the course. Many students we work with have Somali or Chinese Mandarin backgrounds. There are also students from Myanmar, Burma, India and Bangladesh who speak Hakha-Chin, there is a family who speaks Tongan, families from Ethiopia and Kenya that speak Oromo, and two families with Korean. The range of languages within the school change over the years depending on immigration into the area. With such a large proportion of students with EAL in the school, all teachers are teachers of EAL. There is a very clear goal amongst teachers in the school to build EAL students' English literacy and there is an emerging understanding of the importance of students' home languages, however there had not been any practical strategies to bring learners' languages into classrooms prior to the collaboration. So it was within this context that I worked collaboratively with in-service and pre-service teachers to design and trial translanguaging approaches to bring EAL learners' languages into their learning to leverage their overall learning and English language development.

Pedagogic Rationale

There is a need in schools for teachers to recognise and use students' languages as resources for their learning and the Department of Education and Training Victoria (Victorian State Government Department of Education and Training, 2021) and the EAL curriculum (VCAA, 2020) expect it. Predominantly, schools in Melbourne Australia are monolingual English places where languages other than English are not present. This practice does not reflect a valuing of learners' languages that are not English and does not capitalise on the knowledge and skills that these bi/multilingual students have to draw from in their further learning. Therefore, a pedagogic shift towards more linguistically inclusive practices is needed and importantly, a diversity of languages need to not only be seen, heard and valued, but also need to be meaningfully utilised as pedagogical learning resources.

Despite a growing awareness of the importance of learners' home languages in their learning of English as an additional language, many teachers remain unsure how to include home languages in

practice with their EAL learners in their classrooms. For this reason, a collaboration with in-service and pre-service teachers aimed to address this together by designing and trialling translanguaging pedagogies for use with EAL learners in their school context. This rationale underpins the exploratory practice that the following section describes.

Classroom Approach

A collaboration between myself (lecturer-researcher-author), in-service teachers from the school and university pre-service teachers was formed to develop context-specific translanguaging pedagogic strategies for use within this school context. Central to this collaboration was the important sharing of information about each EAL student between in-service and pre-service teachers. The classroom teachers of the EAL students had lots of valuable student information to share with pre-service teachers that supported their work with the students, and in turn, pre-service teachers shared their practice and learnings with the in-service teachers. They had a shared goal to develop students' English language skills, whilst exploring translanguaging pedagogical approaches together. Whilst both in-service and pre-service teachers commented on the need to include students' languages in their learning, there were limited ways that this was currently being done and limited ideas for ways to do this. Therefore, a shared goal of the collaborative team was to learn more about translanguaging and actively trial approaches with EAL learners in their school context. The teacher-practitioner collaboration was supported by me in a range of ways including sharing the theory and research background of translanguaging, joining in planning meetings and discussions of translating translanguaging theory to practice and by sharing past examples of practice that were developed for the same school context (Wilks-Smith, 2021) but had not yet been trialled.

From Theory to Practice

Part of the adoption of translanguaging pedagogies in classroom practice by the in-service and pre-service teachers was an understanding of García, Johnson and Seltzer's (2017) notions of '*stance*', '*design*' and '*shift*'. '*Stance*' refers to teachers' beliefs that learners' languages are resources to think and learn in and that learners should use languages in a meaningful way to them. '*Design*' is needed to plan for learning that will integrate learners' languages. This may include collaborative structures for students to collaborate with other speakers of their languages; a variety of multilingual resources; and translanguaging pedagogical practices (García & Kleyn, 2016). '*Shifts*' may be needed to ensure that classroom practices respond to individual differences in language proficiency and language learning needs. Therefore, "... multilingual strategies and tasks should build on the existing multilingual practices of students" (French, 2019, p.36) and "Tasks should be designed with flexibility to allow students to make choices about how and to what extent they apply their multilingual resources to learning" (French, 2019, p. 38).

The translanguaging design principles of "... valuing students' languages and cultures, modelling translanguaging, providing authentic opportunities for multilingual communication, inviting two-way translation, composing dual-language texts, and connecting students with bilingual or multilingual audiences" (Rowe, 2018, p.31) were also considered in classroom practice and stimulated ideas for the creation of translanguaging approaches to classroom tasks. In the following section which discusses the approaches, these design principles will be evident.

Translanguaging Approaches

There were a range of translanguaging approaches trialled by in-service and pre-service teachers with EAL students one-on-one, in pairs, in small groups and within whole class tasks. The approaches were designed for a purposeful integration of learners' languages into the learning tasks. The collaborative exploration experience was impactful for all involved and a wide range of challenges and considerations, as well as benefits of the translanguaging approach emerged. These are shared as personal reflections, mindful that I am only one member of the collaborative team and the in-service teachers, pre-service teachers and EAL students' feedback was not formally sought. Key learnings are shared in the following sections under 'challenges and considerations' and 'benefits' and examples of the translanguaging approaches are discussed within the themes.

Challenges and Considerations

The greatest challenge that in-service and pre-service teachers faced when considering the concept of translanguaging was how they, as monolingual English-speaking teachers or teachers that do not share the home languages of their students, could practically implement translanguaging as a pedagogic classroom approach. This identified the need for teacher practitioners, both in-service and pre-service, to learn how to translate translanguaging theory to practice that didn't rely on a shared set of languages. So, an integral part of the collaboration was the development of translanguaging pedagogical practices that do not require teachers to know the languages of their students. Rather than teachers playing an active role in using the range of languages in their classrooms, they needed to consider the creation of a classroom environment that would be open to multilingualism and offer flexibility in class tasks that would create opportunities for learners to communicate in their languages, think in their languages, and build their new learning from their knowledge in all languages. This involved a shift in the control of tasks from teachers to students and provided more options for students.

Consideration was needed to be given to students who were the only speakers of their home language/s in the classroom, and possibly even in the school, which was common in this school context and is also common in other similar linguistically diverse school contexts. Therefore, strategies were deployed to consider options for L1 use by single L1 speakers in classrooms as well as utilise like-L1 use where possible in and beyond the school.

A concern held by some teacher practitioners was about not understanding students' work in their home languages. They didn't know what to do with student work or how to respond to it if they couldn't read it or understand it. As will be explained further in the next section, many of the benefits from translanguaging focus on the individual learning benefits for students. Teachers don't need to understand all the students' languages for them to have a learning impact for the students. The following section shows how some of these concerns were overcome and the resulting benefits that were realised.

Benefits of Translanguaging for English Language Learners

Through the process of exploring translanguaging practices in classrooms, a wide range of benefits for English language learners were realised. One significant benefit that was immediately apparent was the authentic home language communication opportunities that translanguaging enabled. Pairs and small groups used their shared home languages to discuss learning content and their work together. This solidified and built on their knowledge and understandings and supported each other's learning. Translanguaging was also used amongst peers to clarify meaning. Students could be heard using key English terms or concepts and then continuing to talk about them in L1. A strategy used with EAL learners was forming same-L1 pairs for sharing work. A common class task is 'turn and talk' or 'pair share' which provides students with time to share their work, discuss it, and consolidate their learning. This was a perfect scenario for translanguaging across languages. Similarly, pairs or small groups could discuss a key question together in L1. This enabled the content to be fully understood before requiring L2 English to be used in class. This shows how translanguaging can help students make sense of content learning. Another example involved same-L1 pairs discussing a topic, then sharing in mixed-language small groups, before a whole class L2 English discussion of the topic. Increasingly building the size of the group and gradually moving from L1 to L2 was a supportive way for EAL learners to practice L2 with familiar content and repetition.

Another key aspect of translanguaging that benefitted EAL learners was the inclusion of an authentic L1 audience so that there was a realistic purpose for L1 use. This could be done where possible in the classroom, or across year levels in the school, but also involved families and community members. An example of this was when families were invited into the classroom for an end of theme project sharing afternoon. Students displayed their work on tables and stood with their projects to talk to families about their work. This provided the opportunity for students to talk about their learning with their parents or family members in their home languages. It gave an authentic purpose for communicating with an audience in L1 and was a way to include L1 with learners who may have been the only speakers of their home languages at school. There were also opportunities to talk about the same project content in L2 English with other students' families. Related to this, home languages were used when creating invitations to families to the project sharing afternoon, and following the event, letters of thanks were written.

Students' use of translanguaging also had an important cognitive function for their learning. It helped students make connections between their prior knowledge in L1 and new knowledge that was developing in L2. One classroom example involved students brainstorming everything they knew on a topic. This is a common classroom task designed to understand students' prior knowledge to build from. When students used translanguaging in this task, they could fully express their knowledge of a topic across their languages. Some knowledge and experiences may only be able to be expressed in one language, so by inviting all languages to be used in a brainstorming task, students were not limited to only include knowledge that they could express in L2 English. The use of L1 activated students' knowledge and schema on a topic and provided a mechanism for them to tap into their knowledge and experiences held in L1 and to demonstrate their knowledge and understandings. This prior knowledge base across languages then becomes a powerful springboard for further learning because it more fully builds on what students know across their languages for their next steps in learning. This example highlights the benefits of translanguaging

for EAL learners and shows that teachers do not need to read all of students' work or understand learners' home languages for translanguaging to have an impact on students' learning.

Another way that students can benefit from translanguaging is by tracking their knowledge over-time, for setting learning goals and to self-assess. A classroom approach that is designed to do these things is a KWL chart. It is used for students to record what they know (K), want to know (W), and then what they have learned (L). When done individually at different points of time across a unit of work, students can see what they knew about the topic at the start, can see their development of knowledge, skills and understandings across the unit of work, and can clearly see their knowledge by the end. Students set their own learning goals and questions to find out about and seek to answer their questions. This puts individual responsibility on students for their learning. When translanguaging is used in the task, the focus of the task is more about the development of curriculum content and conceptual knowledge that can be expressed across languages, rather than being restricted to English which is unlikely to fully portray students' knowledge.

Similarly, when students produce multilingual texts, they may display more information than they may have done in only English, and this may also broaden the audience for their work. A simple but powerful way for languages to be included in school routines is through the recording of home reading of all books in all languages in take-home reading folders. This shows students and their families that sharing books and reading in all languages is a valued and school-relevant task. Another example that includes translanguaging with multilingual texts centres around a language experience. One group of EAL learners participated in a cooking experience together and took photographs of the experience. They then did an oral recount of what they did, supporting each other in home languages and L2 English. This was followed by a written recount in L1 to share the experience with their families at home and a book was made collaboratively in class in L2 English. These opportunities for translanguaging supported students' forming of the language they wished to express, provided student-support to each other, and enabled scaffolded support from a teacher by having multiple exposures to the task content before being asked to perform the written task in English. This method was particularly useful for early L2 English learners who may not have been able to produce any written work if limited to English.

The EAL learners also benefitted from translanguaging for research. This allowed students to use their full range of language skills for researching, reading, thinking about and sorting information, and planning the end product of their research projects. Students searched for information in home languages, read content online, used bilingual dictionaries, and drafted work in L1 or a mix of L1 and L2, before producing the final product, a written report in L2 English. A translanguaging approach supported learners' engagement in the topic and expanded the depth of content learning that they did. Importantly, it offered choice for students to use languages in purposeful, meaningful ways. Languages are tools to use as needed and useful and this practice recognises the diversity in EAL learners' range of skills across modes of language.

When translanguaging is invited into classrooms, it is evident in the classroom linguistic environment. There were multilingual words as labels around classrooms, displays of students' work including home languages, and multilingual books that students brought from home. This addition to the English linguistic environment benefitted EAL learners by recognising their literacy skills in L1 and actively promoting their use of a full spectrum of languages as learning resources.

The benefits of translanguaging also expanded to teachers. Teachers were able to have a better understanding of the EAL learners overall. They developed an increased understanding

of students' literacy capabilities, not limited to English. They also developed an increased understanding of students' content knowledge in a range of curriculum areas. Teachers' observations of students working across languages provided important information about their knowledge and skills, individual needs, and support needed. This diagnostic information was then used to inform their teaching practice.

These reflections illustrate many benefits and practical implications of a translanguaging approach for TESOL and also highlight the collective benefits of a collaborative model for exploring practice in-context together.

Considering Contexts

When considering the benefits of a translanguaging approach in this one school context in Melbourne, Australia, I am very conscious of the intricate contextual variables that can impact on teachers' pedagogical decisions. In particular, I recognise the significant difference in contexts between EAL in an English-dominant-language country and EFL in a non-English-dominant-language country. For EAL learners in an English-dominant-language country such as Australia, at a minimum, students are exposed to English throughout their school days (30 hours per week) and at least to some extent out of school in the community. By contrast, EFL learners in a non-English-dominant-language context, may only be exposed to English in their school timetabled allocation for English as a subject and the teacher of English may be the only speaker of English that they have the opportunity to interact with in English. It is also recognised that in an EFL context where learners' L1s are used as the medium for instruction of L2 English, this further reduces the total time exposed to English. These contrasting contexts and variables differ greatly for English language learners in the overall quantity of time they are exposed to and engaged in English learning and this would certainly impact on their ultimate attainment of English. The EAL and EFL contexts also differ greatly in the level of 'need' that English language learners would have for English. In an EAL context where English is dominant in the environment, it is needed to communicate with the teacher and class peers and to fulfil needs in the community, whereas English may be seen as more of a 'want' in an EFL context to fulfil personal goals and motivations. Also, in an EFL context where learners may have a limited exposure to English, translanguaging may further reduce English time. These contextual and learning differences need to be considered alongside the benefits reported on translanguaging. For this reason, I encourage other teacher-practitioners to consider the translanguaging approach, trial it in their own contexts and share their lived experiences so that the impact of translanguaging in a diversity of contexts is more fully understood.

Conclusions

This article outlined the exploratory practice of a collaborative team of teacher-practitioners to explore translanguaging pedagogical approaches in a linguistically diverse multicultural primary school in Melbourne Australia. Reflective practice was used to illustrate the pedagogical approach, express the challenges faced by teachers, and identify the benefits of translanguaging for English language learners. Translanguaging was shown to provide ways for EAL students to clarify meaning, share knowledge and discuss learning content in L1. Translanguaging also played a cognitive function, enabling EAL learners to connect knowledge in L1 with new knowledge developing in

L2 English. This shows internal benefits for EAL learners and reveals ways to leverage learners' home languages as a platform from which to build further learning. Benefits of the approach also extended to teacher-practitioners who better understood EAL learners' knowledge and learning needs when learners could more fully express themselves across languages, and this was then used to inform teaching practice. The insights about translanguaging pedagogy illustrate its use and benefits in one school context and offer ideas and considerations for others interested in exploring translanguaging in their own context.

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